

Fatty acids and sterols in the seeds of *Cassia auriculata* and *Cassia siamea*

Lalita Ledwani* and Shelley Oberoi

Institute of Petroleum Technology, Pandit Deen Dayal Petroleum University, Raisan, Gandhinagar-382 007, Gujarat, India

E-mail : ledwani_lalita11@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 19 February 2009, revised 8 June 2009, accepted 3 July 2009

Abstract : The comparative study on the composition of fatty acids and sterols in the seed oil of *Cassia auriculata* Linn. and *Cassia siamea* Lam. was carried out. The total oil content in the seeds was found 3.25% in *Cassia auriculata* and 2.99% in *Cassia siamea*. Sterols and fatty acids have been isolated and characterized on the basis of chemical and GC analysis. Three sterols (cholesterol, stigmasterol and β -sitosterol) and four fatty acids (palmitic acid, stearic acid, oleic acid and linoleic acid) were found from the seed oil of both the plants. All compounds were identified by comparison with authentic samples. Linoleic acid, stigmasterol, β -sitosterol were identified as major constituents of the oil.

Keywords : *Cassia siamea*, *Cassia auriculata*, GLC, β -sitosterol, stigmasterol, palmitic acid, cholesterol, oleic acid, linoleic acid, stearic acid.

Introduction

Cassia is a Genus of Fabaceae in the subfamily Caesalpinaceae commonly called Cassias. This is a large dominating tropical genus of about 580 species of herbs, shrubs and trees. Many of them are of medicinal importance and a few are source of tanning material of economic value. Most of the plants of the genus *Cassia* are well known in the Indian system for their cathartic, purgative and antibiotic properties. Species of *Cassia* are rich source of flavonoids, anthraquinone and polysaccharides^{1,2}.

The present paper deals with the isolation and characterization of fatty acids and sterols from the seeds of *Cassia auriculata* and *Cassia siamea*. Both the plants are well known for their medicinal and economic value. *Cassia auriculata* Linn. and *Cassia siamea* Lam., commonly known as Tarwar and Kassod in Hindi. Both sterols and fatty acids exhibit distinct pharmacological activity. Fatty acids are very important in synthesis of tissue hormones, which regulate blood pressure and take part in immunological response. Sterols show anti-inflammatory and immuno-stimulatory activities.

The aim of the study was to compare the composition of sterols and fatty acids in the seeds of both the *Cassia* species^{3,4}. It was considered worth while to isolate the fixed oil from the seeds of *Cassia siamea* and *Cassia auriculata* through GLC technique.

Results and discussion

The total seed oil content was 3.25% in *Cassia auriculata* and 2.99% in *Cassia siamea*.

(A) *Physico-chemical properties* : The physico-chemical properties of extracted oil⁵⁻⁷ samples of both the plants were determined. The oil extracted from the seeds of *Cassia auriculata* and *Cassia siamea* were free from unwanted materials such as glucose, salt, urea, sucrose etc. The seeds contained 4.87% moisture, 20.42% fat, 17.0% protein, 3.98% ash, 7.45% fiber, refractive index 1.467, saponification value 192, iodine value 101.63, unsaponifiable matter 0.45% in *Cassia auriculata* and 5.87% moisture, 22.40% fat, 17.2% protein, 4.08% ash and 7.45% fiber, refractive index 1.457, saponification value 190, iodine value 101.02, unsaponifiable matter 0.52% in *Cassia siamea* (Table 1).

(B) *Sterol characterization* : GLC analysis of the investigated seeds resulted in identifying three sterols namely stigmasterol (18.60%), β -sitosterol (67.50%) and cholesterol (6.716%) in *Cassia auriculata* and stigmasterol (60.01%), β -sitosterol (28.42%), cholesterol (3.51%) in *Cassia siamea* (Table 2). Percentage of β -sitosterol in *Cassia auriculata* and stigmasterol in *Cassia siamea* was quite higher.

Table 1. Physico-chemical characterization of *Cassia auriculata* and *Cassia siamea*

Values	<i>Cassia auriculata</i>	<i>Cassia siamea</i>
Moisture	4.87%	5.87%
Fat	20.42%	22.40%
Protein	17.0%	17.2%
Ash	3.98%	4.08%
Fiber	7.45%	7.45%
Refractive index	1.467	1.457
Saponification value	192	190
Iodine value	101.63	101.02
Unsaponified matter	0.45%	0.52%

Table 2. Sterol composition (relative abundance %) in seed oil of *Cassia auriculata* and *Cassia siamea*

Species	Stigmasterol	β -Sitosterol	Cholesterol
<i>Cassia auriculata</i>	18.60	67.50	6.716
<i>Cassia siamea</i>	60.01	28.42	3.51

(C) *Fatty acid characterization* : The GLC analysis of both *Cassia* species showed that they have uniform and usual fatty acid composition⁸⁻¹¹. It indicated the presence of four fatty acids. The extracted seed oil of *Cassia* species contained significant amount of α -linoleic acid (51.263% in *Cassia auriculata* and 57.20% in *Cassia siamea*), which is one of the most important unsaturated fatty acid. The second major unsaturated acid is oleic acid (20.905%) in *Cassia auriculata* and saturated palmitic acid (19.65%) in *Cassia siamea*. Saturated stearic acid was found in minor percentage (5.797%) in *Cassia auriculata* and (6.43%) in *Cassia siamea* (Table 3).

Table 3. Fatty acid composition (relative abundance %) in seed oil of *Cassia auriculata* and *Cassia siamea*

Species	Palmitic acid (Saturated)	Stearic acid (Saturated)	Oleic acid (Unsaturated)	Linoleic acid (Unsaturated acid)
<i>Cassia auriculata</i>	8.552	5.797	20.905	51.263
<i>Cassia siamea</i>	19.65	6.43	15.99	57.20

Materials and method :

The object of the study was the seeds¹²⁻¹⁵ of two *Cassia* plants i.e. *Cassia auriculata* and *Cassia siamea*. Seeds were purchased from the local market of Ahmedabad. The phytochemical analysis was done in the Department, Petroleum University, Gandhinagar. The result is the mean value from one year.

Cleaned and dried seeds (500 g) of both the

plants¹⁶⁻¹⁸ were crushed and extracted exhaustively with light petroleum ether (60-80 °C) until colourless extract were obtained. Evaporation of solvent under reduced pressure afforded a yellowish oil which was saponified by refluxing with 10% methanolic KOH for 2 h in the atmosphere of nitrogen. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and residue was diluted with water. The unsaponified matter was used for the identification of sterols^{19,20}.

(A) *Physico-chemical values* : The physico-chemical values like iodine value, saponification value, ester value, free fatty acids were determined according to the procedure of British Standard Specification 684. Refractive index was determined with Abbe's refractometer.

(B) *Separation and identification of sterols* : The unsaponifiable material was extracted with ether and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The ether layer was dried and evaporated to afford residue of unsaponifiable matter. The unsaponifiable matter was column chromatographed over silica gel (40 g) and eluted with increasing concentration of diethyl ether in petroleum ether (5, 10, 15, 20%) to afford a solid form. The last elute was crystallized from methanol-diethyl ether. This gave the positive Liebermann-Buchard colour test for sterols. The sterol mixture was dissolved in 2 ml of acetic anhydride-pyridine mixture (2 : 1) and kept for two nights. The solvent was evaporated *in vacuo* and residue was crystallized from methanol. The crystalline acetate derivative was obtained.

The gas liquid chromatography of the acetate deriva-

tive mixture showed three peaks in the gas chromatograms. It indicates the presence of three sterols. The identification of individual sterol was carried out by comparison of the retention time of the unknown sterol acetates with that of standard sterol acetates (Fig. 1).

GLC of sterols (standard and unknown) was performed on OV-17 and DB-17 fused silica column (length 30 m, i.d. 0.3 mm) on Hewlett-Packard (HP5 890A) gas chro-

Fig. 1. The content of free sterols in *Cassia auriculata* and *Cassia siamea*. Ca : *Cassia auriculata*; Cs : *Cassia siamea*.

matograph equipped with flame ionization detector. Operating conditions were carrier gas, (He); flow rate, 30 min/min; injector and detector temperature, 290 °C; column temp. 270 °C isothermal.

(C) *Separation and identification of fatty acid* : The mixed fatty acids were obtained by acidification of the aqueous layer left after extraction of unsaponifiable matter with diethyl ether. The aqueous layer was acidified with dil. HCl to pH 2-3. This was then extracted with diethyl ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The dried extract was concentrated in presence of nitrogen to afford an oily viscous mass. This was esterified with anhydrous methanol in presence of conc. H₂SO₄ for 2-3 h. The esters so formed were extracted with water and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solvent was concentrated under the stream of nitrogen. The methyl esters thus formed were used for GLC.

The methyl esters of standard and unknown fatty acids were dissolved in petroleum ether and injected to GLC column. GLC of the fatty acids were carried out on model, 4890 II series on GLC gas chromatogram equipped with flame ionization detector using stainless steel column (3 mm × 2 m) packed with 20% DEGS on chromosorb and using nitrogen as a carrier gas. The block was maintained at 210, 170 and 220 °C, respectively.

The identification of individual fatty acid was carried out by comparison of retention time of unknown methyl esters of fatty acids with standard fatty acid methyl esters. Presence of four peaks, confirmed the presence of four fatty acids. The characterization of individual mix-

ture of the seed oil of both the plants was carried out by comparing the retention time of unknown fatty acids with that of methyl esters of authentic fatty acid esters (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The content of fatty acids in *Cassia auriculata* and *Cassia siamea*. Ca : *Cassia auriculata*; Cs : *Cassia siamea*.

References

1. B. J. F. Hudson, *J. Am. Oil Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 540.
2. W. W. Christie, *Industrial Crops and Products*, 1999, **10**, 73.
3. L. Ledwani and M. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2005, **44**, 1970.
4. L. Ledwani and M. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2004, **43**, 2257.
5. L. Vitalone and F. D. Goffman, *Bot. J. Linnean. Soc.*, 1999, **129**, 359.
6. J. Singh and J. Singh, *Phytochemistry*, 1987, **26**, 507.
7. A. K. Tripathi and K. R. Gupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 254.
8. O. Kosakowska, Z. Wglarz, M. Sidky, J. Przybyl and A. Geszprych, *Herba Polonica*, 2005, **51**, 23.
9. G. Honghu, C. Zhenzhah, D. G. Rujun and Z. Junhua, *Phytochemistry*, 1998, **49**, 1923.
10. L. Misra and H. Wagner, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2006, **40**, 801.
11. A. Kumar and M. Ali, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2001, **40**, 1284.
12. C. S. Rao and S. S. Nigam, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **54**, 747.
13. A. K. Mondal, A. Dey and S. Mondal, *Res. J. Chem. Environ.*, 1998, **2**, 19.
14. C. Shoppee, "Chemistry of Steroids", Academic Press, New York, 1958.
15. W. W. Christie, "Lipid Analysis", 2nd ed., Pergamon, New York, 1982.

Ledwani *et al.* : Fatty acids and sterols in the seeds of *Cassia auriculata* and *Cassia siamea*

16. D. Nema, S. K. Srivastava and S. D. Srivastava, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 477.
17. K. S. Bilgrani, K. K. Sinna and S. Premalatha, *Curr. Sci.*, 1982, **51**, 138.
18. F. Sosulski, K. Krygier and L. Hogge, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1982, **30**, 33.
19. S. Ivancheva, N. Manolova, J. Serkedjieva, V. Dimov and N. Ivanovska, *Basic Life Sci.*, 1992, **59**, 717.
20. F. D. Gunstone, "An Introduction to the Chemistry and Biochemistry of Fatty Acids and their Glycerides", 2nd ed., Chapman and Hall, 1967, 11.